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ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ACTIVITIES OF THE COMPANY'S SALES NETWORK

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Abstract: In a competitive and uncertain market environment, strengthening a company's marketing focus and making well-informed management decisions requires comprehensive marketing analysis. This is particularly relevant for companies operating in the light industry sector, which is highly sensitive to fluctuations in consumer demand. Therefore, effective product promotion necessitates the application of modern marketing analysis methods. This article analyzes the influence of seasonality and price range on sales volume using the example of a branded carpet retail chain.

Key words: brand network, sales volume, seasonality, assortment, price.

Annotatsiya: Raqobat kuchli va noaniqlik yuqori bo'lgan bozor sharoitida kompaniyaning marketingga yo'naltirilgan faoliyatini kuchaytirish hamda boshqaruv qarorlarini asoslangan holda qabul qilish mazmunli marketing tahlilini talab etadi. Bu ayniqsa iste'mol talabi o'zgarishlariga sezgir bo'lgan yengil sanoat korxonalarini uchun dolzarbdir. Shuning uchun mahsulotni samarali ilgari surish zamonaviy marketing tahlili usullaridan foydalanishni taqozo etadi. Ushbu maqolada brendli gilamlar chakana savdo tarmog'i misolida mavsumiylik va narx diapazonining sotuv hajmiga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: brend tarmog'i, sotuv hajmi, mavsumiylik, assortiment, narx.

Аннотация: В условиях конкурентной и неопределённой рыночной среды усиление маркетинговой ориентации компании и принятие обоснованных управленческих решений требуют комплексного маркетингового анализа. Это особенно важно для предприятий лёгкой промышленности, которые чувствительны к изменениям потребительского спроса. Поэтому эффективное продвижение продукции предполагает использование современных методов маркетингового анализа. В данной статье на примере фирменной сети розничной торговли коврами анализируется влияние сезонности и ценового диапазона на объём продаж.

Ключевые слова: фирменная сеть, объём продаж, сезонность, ассортимент, цена.

INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of analytical work carried out within an enterprise is to strengthen its market position and enhance its competitiveness. Marketing theorists emphasize that the true competitiveness of a manufacturing enterprise is fully manifested only in the marketplace. Hence, the economic potential of an enterprise can be objectively assessed based on an analysis of product demand among consumers and other market participants.

The sale of carpets and floor coverings requires direct interaction with consumers or targeted buyers; therefore, developing a dealer network and branded retail stores represents one of the most effective and widely used strategies for promoting carpet products. An important element of an efficient marketing policy is ensuring geographically comprehensive market coverage while considering seasonality and product price segmentation.

To successfully address these marketing challenges, an enterprise should maintain a functional economic analysis department. The responsibilities of such a unit include conducting economic, production, marketing, and financial analyses of the enterprise's operations, as well as providing a solid justification for management decisions in formulating strategies and tactics aimed at sustaining and strengthening market competitiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing analysis is one of the key tools used to assess a company's performance and commercial success. In scientific and applied literature, this topic is widely researched from the perspectives of economics, management, marketing, and strategic analysis.

The classical definition of marketing analysis is presented in the works of Philip Kotler. According to his approach, marketing analysis is a systematic assessment of all factors influencing marketing effectiveness, including the study of the market, consumers, competitors, and the internal capabilities of the enterprise [1].

The clarification of the term "marketing analysis" and its economic content has been widely discussed in the works of W. Winston [2], E. A. Utkina [3], E. P. Golubkov [4], A. V. Sokolov [5], S. A. Dyatlov [6], G. L. Bagiev [7], and N. K. Malhotra [8]. Based on the analysis of their research, marketing activity analysis in industrial enterprises can be defined as follows: it is a targeted and continuous process of assessing and interpreting information about the marketing environment, integrated into a marketing information system, and aimed at improving the efficiency of an organization's commercial activities.

At the same time, it should be noted that marketing research conducted in our country has evolved by taking into account national characteristics. Significant contributions to the development of marketing theory were made by scholars such as R. Ibragimov, Yo. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva and others. Their studies enriched marketing science with practical recommendations and theoretical foundations adapted to the regional economic environment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Marketing analysis is a methodological toolkit used to describe, interpret, and explain marketing information available to a research subject. In this study, the authors applied econometric analysis of quantitative carpet sales data, conducted classification and grouping of retail outlets, analyzed time periods to identify seasonal sales dynamics, and implemented additional marketing research methods to assess the influence of product assortment and price categories on sales performance. Such a comprehensive approach made it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the company's sales network and determine key market factors affecting consumer demand.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This article examines the methods and tools for marketing analysis of light industry enterprises, with a focus on companies that manufacture and sell carpets and floor coverings. Most enterprises in the light industry are oriented toward end consumers, which prioritizes sales processes alongside production. Marketing activities aimed at delivering carpet products to consumers can be considered as strategically important as manufacturing itself. Therefore, the application of modern direct marketing methods serves as one of the key approaches to enhancing sales efficiency.

The object of this analysis is the chain of branded retail stores SAG EXPRESS, specializing in the distribution of products manufactured by SamAntepGilam LLC. SAG EXPRESS represents a network of specialized carpet and rug retail stores operating across the Republic of Uzbekistan. The project was founded in 2021 as the retail division of SAG and currently includes more than 18 retail units throughout the country.

The chain offers several store formats: XP — flagship showrooms featuring art installations and exclusive collections; XL — stores with an extensive product assortment; and XS — compact express outlets located in central areas of major cities. This multi-format model allows the company to flexibly adapt to different consumer segments and geographic settings. All stores operate in a unified corporate style with standardized pricing policies, which ensures transparency, strengthens brand recognition, and increases customer loyalty.

SAG EXPRESS also maintains an active digital presence, which plays a critical role in product promotion and customer interaction. The company uses online platforms and social media channels to inform consumers about new arrivals, promotions, and featured collections. The official website and store-specific Instagram pages act as direct communication channels, contributing to the steady growth of online sales. Notably, the business has demonstrated active expansion in recent years — more than 10 retail outlets were opened in 2023–2024, reflecting an intensive phase of market scaling.

As of 2023–2024, the SAG EXPRESS network included 18 retail outlets: 4 in Samarkand region, 3 in Navoiy region, 3 in Tashkent city and Tashkent region, 3 in Khorezm region, 2 in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and one retail outlet each in Surkhandarya, Fergana, and Jizzakh regions. The geographical diversification of retail outlets confirms the company's strategic goal of ensuring proximity to customers in key administrative regions. The existence of different store formats (XP, XL, XS, and small-city specialty stores) also highlights a flexible approach to building distribution channels based on regional population density and purchasing behavior.

During the marketing and sales analysis of the SAG EXPRESS network, the following aspects were examined:

- Sales volumes by region and store, with the objective of identifying the most and least efficient retail units and the factors that shape sales performance;
- Effectiveness of store formats (XP, XL, XS), based on comparative revenue and profitability indicators;
- Seasonal and regional demand patterns, influenced by climatic, cultural, and infrastructural characteristics within various regions.

The data sources used for this research include internal sales and operational reports from SAG EXPRESS branded stores of SAG LLC for 2023–2024 [9]. The analysis begins with a general overview of the sales performance of products within the SAG EXPRESS system (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of changes in revenue of SAG EXPRESS branded stores in 2023–2024 (in million soums)

The analysis of SAG EXPRESS revenue dynamics for the period 2023–2024 shows a stable upward trend, increasing from approximately 10 billion soums in January 2023 to 46.5 billion soums in December 2024. This indicates consistent growth and demonstrates the company's strengthening market position. The data also reveal clear seasonal characteristics in sales: peak revenue is observed in December of both years (29.5 billion soums in 2023 and 46.5 billion soums in 2024), which is likely associated with increased pre-holiday demand. The similarity of trends in both years confirms the existence of a persistent seasonal pattern in consumer demand for carpet products.

For a more detailed assessment, revenue indicators of SAG EXPRESS branded stores operating for more than two years were analyzed. The revenue dynamics for seven stores over 2023–2024 made it possible to classify them into three stable performance segments: leaders (XP), mid-range (XL), and developing stores (XS).

The leading segment is represented by the stores SamExpress1 and Magazin Urganch, which show consistently high revenue levels with clear seasonal peaks. Their average monthly revenues range from 7,500 to 8,000 million soums, with maximum values reaching 11,309 million soums (SamExpress1, December 2023) and 8,926 million soums (Urganch, December 2024). The most active sales months are August and November–December.

The mid-range segment includes the stores Xiva, Jizzax, Bekobod, and Termiz, where average monthly revenue varies between 1,200 and 2,200 million soums. These outlets demonstrate moderate but steady growth. For example, the revenue of Jizzax increased from 56 to 1,316 million soums, while Bekobod increased from 373 to 1,674 million soums. Stores in this category show a peak in December, as well as noticeable growth during September–October, which may be associated with pre-holiday purchases and colder seasonal conditions.

The Farg'ona store currently shows comparatively lower revenue indicators, with an average level of approximately 700 million soums and annual growth averaging +240 million soums. Despite lower results, sales dynamics demonstrate potential for improvement, suggesting opportunities for targeted marketing or competitive repositioning in this region.

Seasonality remains a key characteristic across most outlets: December consistently forms the highest revenue peak, while additional growth is observed in August and September. This confirms the influence of seasonality linked to pre-holiday demand, household preparations, and climatic factors. To assess the impact of such factors, both seasonality coefficients and descriptive characteristics of seasonal intensity were calculated. The seasonality coefficient is defined as the ratio of sales in peak and off-peak months, while the nature of seasonality represents an expert or normative assessment of seasonal intensity categorized as high, moderate, or low (Table 2).

Table 2. Classification of stores by revenue and seasonal activity

Group	Stores	Average monthly revenue (million soums)	Seasonality coefficient	Type of seasonality
Leaders	SamExpress1, Urganch	7500–8000	1.6–1.8	High
Average	Xiva, Bekobod, Jizzax, Termiz	1200–2200	1.2–1.5	Moderate
Developing (formerly outsider)	Farg'ona	~700	~1.1	Weak/low intensity

Another important indicator reflecting the effectiveness of marketing activities is the analysis of consumer demand and the study of its structural components. To conduct a detailed demand assessment, a histogram reflecting the “price–sales volume” relationship was constructed for the main branded stores in 2024 (Urganch, SamExpress1, Xiva, Termiz, Farg'ona, Jizzax, and Bekobod). This histogram visualizes changes in sales volume across different price ranges and makes it possible to determine the price levels that generate the highest revenue.

The analysis of the sales structure of these seven stores shows a strong concentration in the price segment up to 200,000 soums, which accounts for 74% to 87% of total sales in each retail outlet. Among them, Magazin Urganch and SamExpress1 demonstrate the most balanced distribution: sales in the segment up to 100,000 soums account for 30% and 32%, respectively, while the 100,000–200,000 soums segment accounts for 47% and 46%. At Magazin Xiva and Magazin Termiz, the share of sales in the mid-price segment (100,000–200,000 soums) constitutes 52% and 55%, which is the highest among all stores, whereas the low-price segment accounts for 26% at both locations.

Sales at Magazin Farg'ona and Magazin Jizzax also indicate stable interaction with budget-oriented customers: the segment up to 100,000 soums represents 34% at both stores, while the 100,000–200,000 soums category accounts for 48% and 51%, respectively. This suggests a consistent market position in attracting price-sensitive consumers (Table 3).

Table 3. Structure of carpet sales distribution by price segments and stores (2024)

Price segment (thousand soums)	Magazin Urganch	Sam Express1	Magazin Xiva	Magazin Termiz	Farg'ona Store	Jizzax Store	Magazin Bekobod
Up to 100	30%	32%	26%	26%	34%	34%	58%
100-200	47%	46%	52%	55%	48%	51%	29%
200-300	15%	15%	15%	13%	12%	9%	10%
More than 400	7%	7%	6%	7%	6%	5%	3%

Across all store locations, the 200,000–300,000 soums price segment remains relatively less developed, accounting for between 9% (Jizzax) and 15% (Urganch, SamExpress1, Xiva). Sales in the above 400,000 soums category represent the smallest share, averaging 5–7%, except in Bekobod, where the share is noticeably

lower. These results confirm that the primary competition among market participants takes place in the sub-200,000 soum segment, which comprises approximately 80% of total sales for almost all analyzed stores.

At the same time, Magazin Bekobod stands out for its highly concentrated structure: 58% of sales fall into the segment below 100,000 soums, significantly exceeding the average, whereas the 100,000–200,000 soums segment accounts for 29%, and the share of products priced above 400,000 soums is only 3%, which is nearly half that of most other stores. These characteristics indicate a strong focus on budget-oriented consumers and emphasize the importance of strategic pricing and assortment management in this region.

Overall, the stability of demand in lower price categories across all analyzed stores highlights the growing relevance of competitive pricing strategies, particularly within the up to 200,000 soums range. This segment forms the core of the market for carpet products and remains a decisive factor in shaping sales volumes and competitive positioning.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Thus, the analysis of sales by retail outlet category and their geographic location shows that demand for SamAntepGilam LLC carpet products varies across different regions of the country. This makes it possible to identify territories where the company needs to strengthen its presence through more active marketing and sales promotion, as well as regions where maintaining market share requires protective measures against intensifying competition. Such comparisons highlight the importance of differentiated regional strategies rather than a uniform sales approach.

In addition, the identified seasonal and price-related consumer behavior patterns indicate that the company's competitive advantage will largely depend on its ability to manage assortment segmentation and pricing strategies tailored to local market characteristics. Strengthening the dealer network in rapidly growing regions, expanding the assortment in dominant price categories (primarily up to 200,000 soums), and introducing loyalty programs in highly competitive markets may enhance customer retention and increase market penetration. Furthermore, the company can benefit from improving analytical monitoring of consumer preferences and digital channel engagement, which will support more agile decision-making and long-term competitive sustainability.

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